
Abandonment of Pet Animals at the Federal University of Amazonas

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ABSTRACT

Pets are abandoned at the Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM). This criminal conduct can be considered a crime in itself, because the person who commits it is the person responsible for the pet. By abandoning the pet at this public institution, the owner affected the institution's environment, causing various environmental imbalances to the fauna, the place, the abandoned species, the government, among others. One of the objectives of this research was to report on the problem of pet abandonment at this federal public educational institution. Through observation, it was possible to conclude that the practice of abandoning the pet is carried out by the owner of the species. The research used the following methodology: bibliographical references of books, articles, classes and the data analysis technique: observation.

KEYWORDS: UFAM, pet. Owner. Abandonment.

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1.INTRODUCTION : The abandonment of a pet occurs due to the lack of commitment, dedication, and responsibility on the part of the pet owner. Many owners shirk their responsibility to care for their pets, discarding them into the environment.

The Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM) is one of many public institutions, which represents several others, where the issue of pet abandonment is prevalent.

The concern with preventing pet abandonment within this institution or any other environment also troubles society, environmentalists, researchers, NGOs, the public authorities, and other advocates. All of them share the interest of protecting these species.

Pet abandonment, in any environment, will continue as long as responsible pet ownership is not a widespread habit among owners, because, unfortunately, there are still no effective and efficient coercive measures to penalize those who commit such acts of mistreatment.

In general, the pet owner will never admit or take responsibility for their lack of commitment to the duty of responsible pet ownership, which they chose to take on when adopting a pet.

The owner will prefer to justify their misconduct with reasons such as: "I abandoned the animal because I moved," "I don't have the financial means to care for it," "The animal's behavior (like barking or meowing) bothers me and the neighbors," "It got sick and I can't afford the treatment," "It's old"... in short, excuses will always be made.

This article represents a study on the reality of pet abandonment in Brazil, and UFAM is yet another example of an environment where this practice occurs. This institution has become a home for many of these species, which have been rejected by their owners.

2. THE PET AND THE TUTOR: This topic will address pets and their tutors. It is important to understand these two characters before discussing the consequences of pet abandonment at the Federal University of Amazonas.

Roman law served as the basis for the Brazilian Civil Code, where animals are defined as possessions, objects, and things. This designation of "objectification" and "thingification" of pets is outdated in its use by the Judiciary.

Between humans and pets, affective relationships have been established. And due to the construction of these interconnections, it would no longer be possible to define these living beings as things or inanimate objects. Therefore, these species are legally recognized as sentient beings¹.

¹ Environmental law gave rise to animal law. It was the precursor to the definition of "sentient beings" for pets. Environmental law, in association with the principles and guarantees of the Constitution and jurisprudence, contributed to the definition of "sentient beings" for pets. Animals display emotional responses, which is why they are classified as "sentient beings".

An animal is a sentient being in the possession of a human. And this possession is responsible guardianship². The tutor is the one who adopts the pet. In the conception of Tom Regan, one of the leading figures in the reflection on animal rights, he argues in his "The Case of Animal Rights" that the moral value of animals is based on their very existence, which gives them intrinsic value. In light of the provisions of the Declaration of Animal Rights adopted by UNESCO in 1978, animals can be defined as sentient beings and, therefore, holders of dignity, given their emotional expressions. Thus, we can infer that they should be included in the moral community, considering their natural identity as beings capable of emotions, feelings, and sensations such as pain, love, fear, and anguish. (Maluf, 2020, p. 88-89). Pets can no longer be referred to as objects or things, due to their sentience. These living beings are capable of expressing their feelings, emotions, and forming bonds of affection with their tutor.

When a pet shows its feelings, it is a "sentient being," and for this reason, it cannot be seen by the law as a thing or an object.

There is a relationship of affection and trust between this species and the tutor. However, the tutor does not always wish to maintain this relationship. In other words, this relationship is not always reciprocated by the tutor.

Unfortunately, there are situations in which pets lose the affection of their tutors, and this becomes evident when the guardians give up their custody of these sentient beings, abandoning them in the environment.

Taking care of a pet means protecting the well-being, sentience, psychology, and physical integrity of that living being.

The pet is a sentient being because it is capable of emotionally suffering and feeling various types of sensations, such as pain, discomfort, frustration, anguish, joy, sadness, and other emotions.

The pet feels the pain of being abandoned in the environment, meaning it understands that it has been disregarded by its owner. Abandoning a pet is to hurt the dignity of this species. In its various forms, violence against animals is a constant in human societies, which ignore or disregard the dignity of the animal as a being that feels, suffers, has needs, and interests. This negative attitude of humans stems from the supposed superiority they attribute to themselves, a cultural phenomenon that the Australian philosopher Peter Singer calls "speciesism," which he defines as "a prejudice or partial attitude in favor of the interests of members of our own species and against the interests of members of other species" (Santana & Oliveira, 2019, p. 118).

By abandoning an animal in the environment, the owner not only committed the criminal and cruel act of abuse but also contributed to other problems, such as environmental, social, political, and economic issues, as well as impacting wildlife and the discarded species itself. The owner should remember that they are responsible for providing the well-being of the species they chose to adopt, and therefore, they cannot discard it into the environment at their own whim.

The owner cannot rid themselves of a responsibility they willingly took on. The pet is dependent on its owner, and for this species to survive, it requires responsible guardianship.

Some requirements of responsible guardianship that should be provided by the owner to the pet include food, health care, attention to the animal's physiology, physical and psychological well-being, so that the sentient being can attain a minimum level of safety, protection, and quality of life.

The quality of guardianship, whether good or bad, depends on the conduct, behavior, common sense, and awareness of the owner.

3. THE ABANDONMENT OF PETS AT UFAM

By abandoning a pet at the Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM), the owner creates problems for the institution, the public authorities, and the discarded living being.

When an owner decides to abandon their pet at UFAM, they are causing social, environmental, economic, and political issues, while also transferring a responsibility they chose to take on to the institution.

A common scene at UFAM is that many students and staff members bring food (such as pet food) to feed the abandoned animals. These items (donated by people at the university) can be seen in various hallways and areas of the federal institution.

Figure 1: Containers with food and water in the UFAM premises.

Source: Compilation by the author, in July 2024.

² Responsible guardianship is also called responsible ownership or responsible care.

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Another common practice among students³ and various people who are part of the institutional environment is giving food scraps to the pets. Some students and staff members seek to provide neutering⁴ for the abandoned pets at UFAM in order to reduce the proliferation of these species. An owner who abandons a pet at the Federal University of Amazonas is clearly not helping to maintain an ecological, healthy, and balanced environment, nor are they contributing to preserving nature, biodiversity, or the wildlife of the institution. An owner who abandons a pet does not respect the nature of that species and does not wish to practice responsible guardianship. The owner should understand or have the awareness that by taking in a pet, they will incur financial expenses, duties, obligations, and responsibilities for this sentient being, which will grow, make noises (such as meowing or barking), get sick, and age. If the pet is not neutered, it will be able to reproduce⁵. The pet is a vulnerable being; it cannot survive on its own. This species depends on the owner's care to live with dignity⁶.

Figure 2: Black cat abandoned at the Federal University of Amazonas institution.

Source: Compilation by the author, in July 2024.

The owner needs to understand their responsibilities, but it is due to this lack of understanding that pet abandonment occurs, whether at the Federal University of Amazonas or in any other environment.

Because of the individual actions of one owner, repeated by others, we have a large number of abandoned pets.

The owner should understand that a pet cannot be considered an object to be discarded, trash, or a thing that can be abandoned, because this species is a sentient being (with feelings and sensations of joy, sadness, stress, and pain...).

The pet, due to its sentience, is able to understand abandonment and rejection. It is because of this understanding that the species is able to assimilate that it has been abandoned.

Figure 3: Cat abandoned at the Federal University of Amazonas institution.

Source: Compilation by the author, in July 2024.

³ The Federal University of Amazonas does not yet offer a veterinary medicine course.

⁴ Many times, in order to pay for the neutering of abandoned animals, students and staff members collect donations from the members of the institution.

⁵ The responsibility for the proliferation of the adopted, taken in, or purchased species lies with the owner, as it is the owner who decides whether the pet will have offspring or not.

⁶ It is the owner who ensures the well-being of the pet through responsible guardianship.

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Abandoning a pet harms the environment, wildlife, and causes imbalances in the environmental system, such as nature, biodiversity, and also to the sentient living being.

It is not in the interest of society, the public authorities, NGOs, researchers, or others involved, for pets to be abandoned in public places.

It is important to emphasize that the most affected victim by this abandonment in the environment, carried out by the owner, is the pet.

4. THE CONSEQUENCES OF PET ABANDONMENT AT UFAM

The Federal University of Amazonas is a public higher education institution in the state of Amazonas and is also one of the most important in Brazil.

According to historical data, UFAM is the first higher education institution in the country, founded on January 17, 1909.

Despite its great reputation, the institution, at this moment, is not just a place for the pursuit of knowledge; unfortunately, according to some staff members, this federal agency is seen as a suitable place to abandon one's pet.

Due to the abandonment of pets at UFAM, this situation has contributed to environmental impacts on the institution's fauna and flora.

One environmental issue arising from this is the lack of sufficient food to meet the needs of these sentient beings abandoned at the Federal University of Amazonas, and the consequence of this has led to the decimation/death of wild animals.

Figure 4: Cat abandoned at the Federal University of Amazonas institution.

Source: Compilation by the author, in July 2024.

The pets abandoned by their owners at UFAM are hunting⁷ wild animals (which roam or live in the surroundings, mainly rodents, sloths, birds, among others).

Another environmental harm that may occur as a consequence of pet abandonment at UFAM is the spread of diseases to human health.

Many of these abandoned animals may be weakened, infected with parasites, sick, and unvaccinated.

Due to these circumstances, they could transmit diseases to people who frequent the area (Article 54 of the Environmental Crimes Law / Law No. 9.605 of 1998).

Article 54. To cause pollution of any nature to levels that result in or may result in damage to human health, or that cause the death of animals or significant destruction of flora. (Planalto website, online, 2023). (Brazilian Environmental Crimes Law).

Unfortunately, these abandoned pets at UFAM can be vectors of many diseases transmissible to humans.

Some examples of diseases transmitted by these abandoned pets, which are without proper health care, include leishmaniasis, fungal infections, mange, rabies, among others.

⁷ This situation is just one of the environmental impacts caused to the fauna and flora of the institution.

The fleas and ticks on these pets are parasites that can also cause other illnesses in individuals.

By abandoning a pet at the Federal University of Amazonas, the owner is causing environmental damage, including degrading the local fauna, as wild animals that once lived there are dying, and many of these sentient beings abandoned at the institution may be carriers of transmissible diseases, which can contaminate people and other animals.

By abandoning a pet at the Federal University of Amazonas, the owner not only avoids their responsibility but also causes several other environmental implications or damages.

The owner's behavior in abandoning a pet in the environment affects many other areas and actors. For example, the Federal University of Amazonas, by receiving the abandoned pets, incurs environmental, financial, institutional, political, economic, and social losses, because the institution is not the natural habitat of these sentient beings.

These species should be in a home with proper responsible guardianship, which should be provided by the owner.

5. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE OWNER PRACTICING RESPONSIBLE GUARDIANSHIP OF A PET

Responsible guardianship is interconnected with the problem of pet abandonment, whether at UFAM or in any other environment, because it is due to the lack of it that these sentient beings are discarded.

Article 2° of the Universal Declaration of Animal Rights⁸ provides an implicit definition of responsible guardianship, as every animal has the right to be respected by humans, whether or not they are the guardian. This is a right acquired by the species. When a guardian practices responsible guardianship, this respect is upheld.

Article 2° of the Universal Declaration of Animal Rights briefly outlines responsible guardianship for a pet. It is a written proof of certain behaviors that a pet guardian should practice. Responsible guardianship is realized when the guardian provides attention, affection, health, security, a home, and various other types of care to maintain the protection of the species.

If the guardian truly wanted to uphold the responsibility or obligation they took on when they decided to welcome, adopt, or purchase a pet, they should not abandon this sentient being in the environment.

5.1. The view of the Federal Constitution regarding responsible guardianship of pets

The Federal Constitution, in its article 225, item VII, addresses the protection of wildlife, and pets are part of it.

When a guardian abandons a pet in the environment, they subject it to cruelty, as the sentient being requires the care of responsible guardianship to survive.

The pet needs the guardian's company, as it is the guardian who ensures the well-being of the species and maintains the care necessary for the survival of this sentient being.

By abandoning a pet in the environment, the guardian harms their own species, constitutional principles, the environment, wildlife, the Penal Code, other norms, laws, and ethical and moral principles.

The Brazilian Federal Constitution (CFB) implicitly prohibits the practice of abandoning pets in the environment, as it is in everyone's interest to have an ecologically balanced environment with quality of life, free from acts of cruelty.

Therefore, a guardian who abandons a pet in the environment violates a foundational guarantee of a constitutional principle.

Article 225. Everyone has the right to an ecologically balanced environment, a common good of the people and essential for a healthy quality of life, with the duty of the Public Power and the community to defend and preserve it for present and future generations.

VII – protect wildlife and flora, prohibiting, as prescribed by law, practices that endanger their ecological function, cause the extinction of species, or subject animals to cruelty. (Brazilian Federal Constitution, Planalto website, online, 2024).

It is in the interest of the Federal Constitution to ensure a healthy and high-quality environment for: people, nature, and pets (which are part of wildlife and biodiversity).

Item VII of §1 of article 225 of the Constitution is an example of a biocentric⁹ perspective, as it reflects a concern for the well-being of these sentient beings.

For the Federal Constitution, the lives of pets are important.

Therefore, the view of the Federal Constitution regarding responsible guardianship¹⁰ of pets indirectly addresses the idea that it is the duty of society and the State to ensure the protection and rights of this species, ensuring that guardians fulfill their responsibilities.

⁸ The Universal Declaration of Animal Rights (UDAR) was proclaimed by UNESCO at a session held in Brussels, Belgium, on January 27, 1978.

⁹ The biocentric perspective does not view humans as the central figure or the only ones with value. Biocentrism advocates that all lives have value. In other words, this philosophy recognizes the value of the lives of non-human animals, as well as of wildlife and plants. According to the biocentric theory, all other living beings are interdependent with the human species. Therefore, it is also concerned with the protection of pets and asserts that they possess inherent dignity and value. The sentience of animals is defended by biocentrism.

¹⁰ Responsible guardianship could become something cultural, a common practice in Brazil. However, what is culturally practiced is the abandonment of pets in the environment (which becomes a dumping ground for these species).

5.2. The dissemination of Environmental Education about Responsible Guardianship of Pets

Responsible guardianship is a form of respect by the guardian towards the pet, and practicing it is a way to ensure the rights and protection of these species and the environment. The criminal behavior of some guardians who abandon their pets in the environment makes it seem as though these animals are treated as disposable objects with no value.

To prevent the abandonment of pets from continuing to perpetuate in the environment, it is necessary to disseminate, improve, and implement environmental education on responsible guardianship, aimed at society and especially at those who own or wish to own such species. Environmental education is a tool that can help responsible guardianship become a common practice, a social and environmental culture in our society. Environmental education on responsible guardianship of pets and the preservation of the environment, in order to become a habit, a custom, a culture in our country, needs to be learned and practiced by both guardians and the population. Responsible guardianship is an internalized practice, as once it is understood in its conceptualization, it can be applied externally, meaning it can become a concrete concept, reflected in the guardian's actions.

In the words of Leff (2015, p.246): "learning is a process of producing meanings and a subjective appropriation of knowledge. In this sense, the educational process helps to form new social actors, capable of leading the transition to a democratic and sustainable future." These new actors can be characterized by the guardians who practice responsible guardianship of their pets.

The practice of responsible guardianship by a pet guardian would represent learning as a process of producing meanings and knowledge that were instilled through the subjective educational process.

Environmental education of the guardian of a pet can only occur when they are willing to learn about the educational process of the meanings and subjective knowledge of responsible guardianship.

A guardian who chooses to apply responsible guardianship for their pet contributes to the conservation of the environment.

6. CONSIDERATIONS: The Federal University of Amazonas represents another environment that shelters pets abandoned by their guardians. When a guardian abandons their pet in a public institution such as UFAM, they engage in a criminal act of mistreatment and, moreover, violate environmental, ethical, and moral principles by refusing to practice responsible guardianship of the sentient being they chose to adopt. One solution to reduce the problem of pet abandonment at UFAM would be raising awareness through environmental education on responsible guardianship as the first step. A pet abandoned at UFAM or in any other environment has its rights violated and disrespected, not only in the legal, environmental, constitutional, and penal sense but also morally and ethically. One of the objectives of this research was to generate a relevant and poignant reflection on the issue of pet abandonment at UFAM.

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